

UAP Orbs: Magnetically Confined Dusty Plasmoids Produced by Meteors

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Abstract: *One of the most commonly reported Unidentified Aerial Phenomena (UAP) is a large, bright luminescent ball of light in the lower troposphere colloquially known as an “orb.” Analysis of 508 orb sightings reported to the National UFO Reporting Center (NUFORC) found that these silent, floating balls of light exhibit plasma-like behaviors and can emit light of a wide variety of colors for up to several hours. In this work, citizen science reports of orb and fireball observations are shown to be highly correlated (3σ), and it is proposed that orbs are a natural and previously unknown type of dusty plasma produced by stabilization of electrically charged meteoric dust in the lower atmosphere. Estimates show that remanent magnetization of meteoritic particles could provide containment of a weak plasma and that energy harvesting from the atmosphere through the triboelectric effect could provide sufficient energy for buoyancy, plasma behavior and light emissions.*

Introduction

Luminous spheres in the atmosphere, colloquially known as “orbs,” are one of the most frequently reported types of Unidentified Aerial Phenomena (UAP), with hundreds of reports of orb observations filed each year. This paper includes a partial review of citizen reports of glowing orbs filed online with the National UFO Reporting Center (1). Those reports, which include written descriptions, photos and videos, provide insight useful in formulating a plausible theory of the physics of orb formation and behavior. Some characteristics of orbs that need to be explained include: (1) an adequate source of energy to provide buoyancy and light emission; (2) a means of confining the glow to an approximate sphere; (3) long life of up to several hours, (4) a range of colors covering the entire visible spectrum, sometimes changing colors or flashing different colors; (5) a corona with sparking into surrounding air; (6) frequent observations of many orbs traveling together; (7) weak binding of two or more orbs with “bond lengths” of up to ~1-2 orb diameters; (8) merging of orbs and splitting of orbs to form two or more orbs; (9) blinking on and off of orb emissions; and (10) glowing orbs inducing emissions from nearby dark orbs.

A theory, based on a meteoric origin of orbs, is presented that potentially accounts for all of these features. The initial energy for orb formation is supplied by the high initial kinetic energy of the meteoroid which impacts the atmosphere at tens of km/s. Depending on composition, velocity and angle of impact, meteoroids of up to several cm in diameter are completely vaporized as they transit the atmosphere. As the resultant fireball cools, nanometer-sized particles of metals, silica and other materials are formed by condensation and become highly charged due to friction

with air. Magnetite and other iron and nickel oxide particles become magnetized as they cool through their Curie temperatures in the presence of the magnetic fields created by ion currents within the fireball. These charged particles with remanent magnetization are key to formation of a “dusty” (aka “complex”) plasma (2) where confinement of the plasma is provided by magnetic attraction exceeding electrostatic repulsion of like-charged particles. Energy stored in the electric field powers plasma and micro-discharges in air to produce the observed visible radiation, but the electric field must be continuously regenerated to maintain emissions over periods of minutes to hours. Tribocharging (3) through repeated nanoparticle contacts is proposed as a means of continuous harvesting of mechanical energy from ambient air to maintain a weakly charged plasma and buoyancy. Thus, in this theory, orbs result from a natural phenomenon – the formation of a previously unknown type of plasmoid (magnetically contained plasma) from meteoric dust upon termination of meteors within Earth’s lower atmosphere. Unique to this type of plasmoid is remanent magnetization of the particles themselves providing the magnetic confinement.

Analysis of Luminous Orb Data Reported on the National UFO Reporting Center (NUFORC) Website

NUFORC provides an online means for individuals to provide reports of observations of what formerly were known as Unidentified Flying Objects (UFOs) and are now referred to as Unidentified Aerial Phenomena (UAP) (4). Reports are made online and available to the public since the launch of their website in 1995. To date, more than 160,000 reports have been filed online. Reports consist of date, time, duration and location of observation, color, number and shape of the UAP, speed of movement and many other factors. Importantly, a small fraction of reports includes uploaded photos and videos. The presence of media makes it possible to attribute many observations to known phenomena such as planets, stars, rockets, meteors, sky lanterns, etc. Because a large fraction of reports can be attributed to natural or other phenomena unrelated to orbs, we limited our study to reports with imagery. Also, due to limited reports in early years, data analyzed here are confined to the inclusive period 2000-2025. During this period, 1,296 reports responding to the search term “orb” contained photos and/or videos. Those reports were examined in random order and either accepted or rejected as likely being reports of luminous orbs--defined simply as unexplained glowing spheres of light in the sky. Minimal criteria for acceptance were (1) having credible imagery, (2) observation of luminance (therefore almost entirely nighttime) of an object in the sky and (3) no associated solid structures. Reports included annotations by NUFORC of many sightings likely being balloons, aircraft, drones, rockets (with specific launch dates), sky lanterns, planets, meteors, stars, the moon, space junk, Starlink, the International Space Station, searchlights, birds, insects, camera anomalies, etc. The final assessment generally agreed with NUFORC except in the instance of sky lanterns, which were mostly reassigned as orbs. Additionally, observations were rejected in cases of (1) narrative statements that the reported phenomena occur frequently, (2) regular blinking of red and/or green lights at ~1 Hz indicative of drones or aircraft, and (3) sudden acceleration suggestive of drones. The goal was to reduce the data set to those most likely to represent a single class of UAP (referred to here as “orbs”) with similar characteristics such that observations could be further analyzed for correlations with other

parameters such as fireball observations, periods of meteor showers, meteorological parameters, etc. Examination of the reports also revealed observations of orbs in associations with meteors, as further addressed below. Of the reports examined, 508 (39%) were accepted as likely observations of orbs for this study, of which 408 were observations made in the US.

Summary of Characteristics of the Orb Class of UAP

Shape, Size and Color. The most often reported orb is a bright white or bluish white sphere, observed to be as bright or brighter than Venus and larger by a factor of several diameters. Many are a yellowish white, while others are orange or even bright red. A few are blue or green. Many observers report that orbs flicker or sparkle in one or more colors, including all colors of the rainbow, and many report that the orb is surrounded by a corona. Estimated sizes range from that of a basketball to that of a house or even larger, but often there is no estimate of size because of a lack of a reference point against the dark sky. The median reported size is approximately in the range of 1-3 m. Orbs occur singly, but about as often with 1-10 or more other orbs of varying sizes, brightnesses and sometimes colors. Observers often report that orbs continuously change shape but on average are spherical. Examples of seven orb photos (5), some from video frames, are provided in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Seven examples of orb photos showing the wide variety of colors, a corona and the bonding (e) of orbs.

A fuzzy, thin corona that is ~5-15% of the orb diameter is apparent in nearly all of these photos, and what appear to be multicolored microdischarges from the surface are best seen in the video associated with Fig. 1b (6). Figure 1e shows contact and longer distance bonding of three blue and green orbs (7). It should be kept in mind that nearly all photos and videos were obtained with smart phone cameras, which are known to have associated artifacts due to optics, autoexposure, autofocus, image processing and spread of images of distant objects over a small number of pixels that affect shape, color and other image properties. But many aspects like flickering of colors, changes in shape and coronas were often reported as being confirmed by direct unassisted visual observation and by using scopes and binoculars. Orbs are observed to persist for times ranging from a few minutes to several hours. Often, they just blink out, possibly explaining some reports that they sped away at incredible speeds. They make no sound and typically move slowly. Observers sometimes report that one or more orbs moved against the wind, but wind direction often changes with altitude. It is more likely that orbs simply move with the wind, sometimes rising and sinking due to internal temperature changes.

Plasma Behavior. The above-mentioned descriptions are suggestive of orbs being confined plasmas. In fact, some observers use the term “plasma” or even “plasmoid” to describe them in their reports. Some of the strongest evidence for plasma behavior is provided by photographic and video evidence of multiple orbs interacting with one another. There are reports of orbs splitting into two or more orbs (8) and of two orbs combining into a single orb. A single orb sometimes has one or more satellite orbs that appear to be captured in its electric field such that they move together. A good example of some of these behaviors is shown in Fig. 2, which contains cropped frames of a video where two orbs approach each other and reorganize into an agglomerate of three orbs.

Fig. 2. Cropped frames from the video associated with NUFORC Report 194306.⁹ Times are relative to the frame in the upper left corner. Video obtained on 22 Nov 2025 at 20:10 local time in the Estrella Mountains outside of Gila Bend, AZ.

This agglomerate then splits off one orb, followed by the remaining two orbs merging (best seen in the video) (9). Note that the colors of different orbs vary from frame to frame, and when the orbs are close, there is a reddish-brown glow that appears to be light scattering from the interstitial spaces—possibly from meteoric dust being exchanged or lost. In some cases, orbs suddenly appear and disappear as suggestive of plasma ignition and quenching (10). Some orbs flash at a very fast rate with nearby dark orbs sometimes flashing synchronously (11). These observations are strongly indicative of plasma behavior where discharges in one orb can be triggered by fluctuations in the electric field of another nearby one. If orbs are dusty plasmas, the weak binding of two or more orbs, as seen in Fig. 1e and Fig. 2, would be expected, as a result of charge-induced dipole, dipole-dipole and other multipole electrostatic interactions associated with non-uniform internal charge distributions. Magnetic dipole attractions between orbs also would be expected and could contribute to orb binding if they contain magnetized particles, as discussed below.

Coincidence of Observations of Orbs and Meteors

Fireballs are bright meteors conventionally defined as appearing brighter than Venus. The American Meteor Society (AMS) maintains a citizen-science database of fireball observations, in which multiple individual reports are grouped into single fireball events, each event being characterized by time and location. The database is searchable by country and U.S. state, enabling geographically constrained comparisons.

To test for a correlation between orb sightings reported to NUFORC and fireball observations reported to the AMS, the AMS fireball database was searched for events occurring within 3 h before or 4 hours after each orb observation. Matches were binned into seven 1-h intervals. To minimize heterogeneity in reporting practices and observational bias, the analysis was restricted to U.S. states, where the overwhelming majority of both orb and fireball reports originate from amateur observers using similar observational platforms.

Temporal correlation of orb and fireball observations. During the inclusive period 2020–2025, a total of 408 U.S. orb observations meeting the selection criteria described above were identified. Of these, 94 coincided with at least one AMS fireball report in the same state during the 3 hours before an orb observation and 4 hours after (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Number of fireball events occurring within 1-hr periods relative to observation of an orb in that state. Bin 0 represents the 1-hr period following observation of an orb. Error bars are 1σ .

The temporal distribution of these coincidences is strongly peaked near the time of orb observation: 60 fireballs occurred within ± 1 h of an orb observation, compared with 8 fireballs during the 2 preceding hours (-3 to -1 h) and 45 fireballs during the 3 following hours ($+1$ to $+4$ h).

If bright fireballs were isolated, singular events, correlations with orb observations would be expected primarily, if not exclusively, during the ~ 1 h interval immediately preceding an orb report. Instead, comparable excesses of fireball reports are observed both before and after orb sightings. This temporal symmetry is inconsistent with a one-to-one causal association between a single detected fireball and a subsequent orb observation. However, this pattern is naturally explained by the well-established tendency for meteoroids to arrive in temporally clustered groups rather than as isolated events (12-13). Fine-scale structure within meteoroid streams—such as dust trails and filaments—produces enhanced meteor activity over timescales of tens of minutes to several hours (14,15). Because only a small fraction of meteoroid entries are actually detected and reported, an observed fireball frequently serves as a proxy for multiple nearby meteoroid entries, including additional fireballs that may have occurred earlier or later but went unobserved. Under these conditions, observed orb–fireball coincidences extending 1–2 h both before and after an orb report are expected.

Estimation of the random background coincidence rate. In order to assess statistical significance, it is necessary to establish the expected background rate of random orb–fireball coincidences. A naïve comparison between the ± 1 h bin and more distant bins yields an apparent excess at very high confidence ($Z \approx 5$), but this approach does not account for strong time-of-day variations in observational efficiency. Both orbs and fireballs are more frequently observed during the early nighttime hours, particularly within ~ 1 – 2 h after sunset when it is sufficiently dark but citizen observers are not sleeping. Also, a substantial fraction of the -3 to -2 h and -2 to -1 h bins fall during daylight, artificially suppressing the apparent background rate due to poor visibility.

To remove time of day as a confounding variable, we therefore compared fireball counts during the ± 1 h window surrounding each orb observation with fireball counts during the same local time windows on the day before and the day after each orb observation. Results from both analyses are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Numbers of Fireballs Reported Relative to Times of Orb Sightings

	Time Relative to Orb Sighting, hr						
	-3 to -2	-2 to -1	-1 to 0	0 to 1	1 to 2	2 to 3	3 to 4
Day before			18	14			
Day of	5	3	27	33	18	13	14
Day after			18	21			

From the day-before and day-after comparisons, we estimate the random background rate of coincidental orb and fireball sightings to be 17.8 ± 2.9 . This value is consistent with the 18 fireballs observed in the $+1$ to $+2$ h bin on the actual day of orb sightings and is modestly higher than the 13 and 14 fireballs observed in subsequent hours. In contrast, only 3 and 5 fireballs were observed in the -2 to -1 and -3 to -2 periods, respectively, on the same day of orb observation, reflecting an observational bias of fireballs during those periods, many of which are during daylight hours.

An independent estimate of the average background rate can be obtained from the overall AMS fireball statistics. In 2025, 10,443 fireball events were reported over 4,380 daylight hours across 51 U.S. states and districts, corresponding to an average probability of 0.0467 for observing a fireball in any given state during any single hour. For 408 orb observations, this implies an expected 19.1 random orb–fireball coincidences per 1-h interval. When weighted by the distribution of fireball and orb reports over the full 2020–2025 period, the expected background becomes 17.1, in excellent agreement with the 17.8 ± 2.9 value derived from the day-before/day-after analysis.

Statistical significance. The significance of the excess fireball rate during the orb ± 1 h window relative to the background rates on the day before and day after orb observation is most appropriately evaluated using a conditional binomial test. The null hypothesis is that the fireball rate during the orb’s ± 1 h window is identical to the rate at the same local times on adjacent days. A total of 60 fireballs were observed during the orb ± 1 h window ($T_1 = 2$ h), while a total of 72 fireballs were observed during the corresponding windows on the day before and day after ($T_2 = 4$ h), yielding a total of $n = 132$ fireballs. Under the null hypothesis, the expected number during the orb window is $E = pn$, where $p = T_1/(T_1 + T_2) = 1/3$, giving $E = 44$. The variance is

$$\sigma^2 = np(1 - p) = 132 \times \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{2}{3} = 29.3, \quad (1)$$

and thus $\sigma = 5.42$. The resulting Z-score is $Z = (60 - 44)/5.42 = 2.95$. A Poisson rate-ratio test yields a consistent value of $Z = 2.99$. Thus, the null hypothesis can be rejected with >99% confidence (one-sided $p \approx 0.003$; two-sided $p \approx 0.006$), demonstrating a highly significant statistical correlation between orb observations and enhanced fireball activity.

Direct Reports of Orb and Meteor Associations. There are several submitted reports, as summarized in Table 2, of observations of orbs almost immediately after seeing a meteor. These eyewitness observations reinforce results of the statistical analysis presented above that demonstrates a strong correlation of orb and fireball observations by independent observers.

Table 2. NUFORC reports of meteors becoming orbs.

Observation	NUFORC Report No.
“I was in my backyard checking whatever, turned to look into the night sky and see a light blue what I thought was a comet falling from the sky. It started turning and dimmed down to an orb.” The report includes a video of a bright white orb. (2023-04-03, 20:38 Local, Fort Worth, TX) (16).	177770
“The sighting occurred shortly after I observed the largest and brightest falling star I have ever seen. Moments after the meteor disappeared, two glowing orange orbs appeared in the sky.” The report contains a video showing two orbs. (2024-12-30, 21:21 Local, Hereford, TX) (17).	187380
“I was ready to leave my driveway around 8pm on Saturday September 16, 2023 and was startled to observe a short flash, very defined light burst where I looked up to the left in the dark sky, which appeared similar to a falling star but much shorter and wider, and probably a mile high. It then stopped and turned into a round bright light.” The report includes a video of an orb and two photos. (2023-9-16, 20:00 Local, Levittown, NY) (18).	178308 179172

“... I noticed a bright light emerging high in the sky. At first, it appeared to be a meteor plummeting into the atmosphere with a fairly straight downward trajectory. It looked small but noticeable, burning with a bright red-orange glow. ... Its descent eventually came to a stop just above the cloud line, and then it started moving back and forth—side to side—without changing altitude. The object continued to emit light, appearing to radiate from itself.” Still photos show an orange orb. (2025-04-01, 21:40 Local, Tacoma, WA) (19).	189721
“Shortly after noticing what appeared to be an asteroid, I observed a separate object enter my field of view from the north and travel smoothly toward the south. The object was completely silent and moved at a steady, controlled pace. (2025-12-14, 00:48 Local, Albuquerque, NM) (20).	194726

One other report provided continuous video of what appeared to be a meteor transitioning into an orb (21). However, based on angle of entry and the long entry time of greater than 40 s, (meteor entries typically occur in less than 1s), this video is almost certainly the reentry of the Genesis 2 experimental space habitat (NORAD ID 31789), which was deorbited within a few minutes of the reported observation time (22). The video is very useful, however, in showing how a mass entering the atmosphere can form a stabilized glowing sphere (Fig. 4) that persists for at least 1 min. Whether this object became a long-lived orb is unknown. There probably aren't enough orbital reentries (820 in 2025) (23) to account for the number of reported orb observations due to most being controlled to fall over open oceans, but it is possible that they contribute to orb formation. Satellites are composed mostly of aluminum, but booster rockets contain large amounts of iron, which, as hypothesized below, may provide orb containment through magnetization.

The high correlation between orb and meteor observations in combination with eyewitness reports leads to the hypothesis that orbs are derived from impacts of some subset of meteors that reach the troposphere. The remainder of this paper addresses the difficult questions of how orbs formed from the remnants of meteors could remain intact, exhibit plasma-like behavior and emit electromagnetic energy for up to several hours.

Fig. 4. Reentry of Genesis 2 experimental space habitat. Frame captures from NUFORC Report 192238. Upper image at time ~20 s. Lower image is of the luminescent semi-stabilized remnant at ~51 s. In the video, light emission from the fireball extinguishes at time ~41 s, then reappears much brighter at ~50 s.

Meteors as Sources of Energy and Particulate Matter

Because of their high velocities of tens of km/s, meteor impacts with the atmosphere provide an enormous source of energy. Meteor entry velocities are in the range 11-72 km/s, such that a 1-kg meteor has an initial kinetic energy in the range 61 MJ to 2.6 GJ. Only a tiny fraction of this energy is required to initially vaporize and ionize most or all of the meteoroid to form a fireball. As the fireball cools, vaporized silica, iron, nickel and other components condense to form nanometer-sized particles (24, 25). In addition to providing sufficient initial energy, the frequency of meteor impacts with the atmosphere are orders of magnitude more frequent than required to account for the rate of orb observations. A widely used empirical normalization for the cumulative number of impacts on the atmosphere by meteoroids in the size range of millimeters to meters is given by

$$N(> D) \approx 3.7 \times 10^7 D^{-2.7} \quad (2)$$

where D is the diameter in meters (26). Table 2 shows the estimated number of meteoroid impacts in the size range 1 cm to 1 m per year. The fraction of meteors being reported by people is extremely low due to most (>95%) of the surface area of Earth being uninhabited, meteors being noticeable primarily at night while most people remain indoors, only a small fraction of meteors being bright enough to see, and only a small fraction of observers filing reports. As discussed below, meteors reaching the troposphere and forming observable orbs are likely in the tens of cm diameter range. Considering that only a small fraction of meteors might form orbs, and with less than one reported orb observations per day, there are enough impacts of 50-cm meteors, for example, to allow a combined meteor-to-orb conversion, observation and reporting efficiency of less than less than 1.5×10^{-6} .

Table 2. Approximate numbers of meteoroid impacts with the atmosphere per year based on equation (2).

Diameter, cm	No. of impacts per year
1	9.3×10^{12}
2	1.4×10^{12}
3	4.8×10^{11}
5	1.2×10^{11}
10	1.9×10^{10}
50	2.4×10^8
100 (1 m)	3.7×10^7

Formation, charging and total electrical energy of a dusty plasma. The extremely high temperature of a meteor fireball results in melting, vaporization and at least partial ionization of its components. For stony meteoroids (chondrites), components include silicate minerals such as olivine and pyroxene and smaller amounts of iron, nickel and sulfide minerals, while carbonaceous chondrites also contain water and carbon. Iron-nickel meteoroids typically are almost entirely composed of an alloy of iron (90-95%) and nickel (5-10%) (27). It is the iron and nickel that likely

plays the most important role in orb formation because both are ferromagnetic. Even chondrites, which are the most common meteorites found, contain up to ~20% of iron and nickel, depending on type (28). Vaporization is followed by condensation to form small liquid and then solid nanometer-sized particles (“grains” in physics parlance) as the fireball cools during the fraction of a second to at most the few seconds it takes for the fireball to pass through the atmosphere.

.A small fraction of meteor strikes will produce fireballs that terminate in the troposphere (~0-12 km altitude), and those balls of meteoric dust will be highly charged. The total amount of charge present on the particles determines the electric field strength, which in turn is limited by the breakdown electric field strength in the atmosphere of ≈ 30 kV/cm. If the particles were confined by a sphere, because of mutual repulsions they would form a thin sheath on the surface of that sphere. We can use the equation for capacitance of an isolated conducting sphere, which depends only on the radius R of the sphere, to estimate the total charge that can be stored,

$$C = 4\pi\epsilon_0 R \quad (3)$$

where C is the capacitance (q/V), ϵ_0 is the permittivity of space (8.854×10^{-12} F/m). Substituting C into the equation for the potential energy of a charged capacitor, $E = CV^2$, we have

$$E = 4\pi\epsilon_0 R V^2 \quad (4)$$

for the total energy of our charged sphere. Because of the breakdown electric field strength in air at ground level of ≈ 30 kV/cm, the most energy we can store on a 1-cm diameter (0.5 cm radius) meteoroid is calculated from equation 3 to be only 6.26×10^{-5} J. If after passing through the atmosphere it vaporizes and forms N smaller spherical particles, it turns out that the total energy stored in the particle cloud is exactly the same, regardless of particle size. The reason is that the breakdown voltage scales with diameter of the particle. For example, if a 1-cm diameter sphere is divided into 8×10^{15} spherical particles of diameter 50 nm, the applied voltage before breakdown is only 0.075 V and the capacitance of the particle is 2.78×10^{-18} Farad. The energy per particle, $\frac{1}{2}CV^2$, is 7.82×10^{-21} J, and the total energy of all particles is 6.26×10^{-5} J, the same maximum energy that be stored on the 1-cm spere itself. The total energy scales linearly with the diameter of the meteoroid before ablation, so even a 1-m meteoroid can store a charge of no more than 6.26 mJ, which is an inconsequential amount of energy. Even with 100% efficiency, it could provide a 10-watt light source for only 0.6 milliseconds. Thus, although the meteor has many MJ of initial kinetic energy, only a miniscule amount can be partitioned into electrical energy of the orb that it forms. As discussed below, in order to maintain its plasma properties and emit tens or more watts of light over periods of up to a few hours, it needs a continuous source of energy. But before addressing that question, first we need a means of plasma containment.

Magnetic confinement of a dusty plasma. Without a restoring force, charged particles remaining after termination of a meteor trail in the atmosphere would rapidly disperse due to electrostatic repulsion and atmospheric mixing. In laboratory plasmas, confinement requires extremely strong externally applied magnetic fields; however, the magnetic fields associated with

the motion of charged particles alone are orders of magnitude too weak to confine a plasma in the free atmosphere. Instead, we propose that the restoring force arises from remanent (permanent) magnetization of the condensed particles themselves.

Metallic iron and nickel are ferromagnetic, while magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), both commonly reported in meteoritic dust, are ferrimagnetic. As particles formed in fireballs cool below their respective Curie temperatures (770°C for Fe, 358°C for Ni, 583°C for magnetite and 617°C for maghemite), any aligned magnetic dipole orientations can become locked in as remanent magnetization, forming permanent nanoscale magnets. Although Earth's magnetic field is too weak to magnetize these particles significantly, magnetic fields generated by plasma currents collisional processes during meteor entry are evidently sufficient to induce alignment, as evidenced by the strong magnetic response routinely observed in collected meteoritic dust (29). Such remanent magnetization provides a natural restoring force capable of contributing to confinement of a weakly charged dusty plasma.

Balance of electrostatic and magnetic forces to provide a spatially confined spherical orb. Here we provide a simple model of orb stability. The electrostatic repulsive force between any two identical particles is

$$F_E = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{q^2}{r^2} \quad (5)$$

where q is the charge on the particle and r is the distance between the centers of the particles; i.e., r would be the particle diameter (not radius) if the particles were touching. A magnetized particle behaves like a dipole of moment m where the strongest dipole-dipole attraction occurs when particles are aligned head-to-tail. The resulting force is

$$F_M = \kappa \frac{3\mu_0 m^2}{2\pi r^4} \quad (6)$$

where μ_0 is the vacuum magnetic permeability ($1.257 \times 10^{-6} \text{ N}\cdot\text{A}^{-2}$) and κ is an orientation packing factor, varying from 0 to 1 where $\kappa = 1$ implies perfect head-to-tail alignment (chain formation). Due to random motions and the 3-dimensional structure, however, $\kappa < 1$. We may then set the repulsive force F_E equal to the attractive magnetic force F_M , substitute the fundamental relationship $\mu_0\epsilon_0 = 1/c^2$ where c is the speed of light and solve for a critical value of separation r_c where the electrostatic repulsive and magnetic attractive forces are equal:

$$r_c = \frac{\sqrt{6\kappa}}{c} \frac{m}{q} \quad (7)$$

At separations greater than the critical distance r_c , the net force is repulsive, and particles will accelerate away from one another and the orb will disintegrate. Particles closer than the critical distance r_c will feel greater magnetic attraction than repulsion and thus will be drawn into contact with one another. Thus, if the charge becomes high enough that the critical distance is less than the particle diameter, the particles will separate and disperse. Because the particle charge is limited by the breakdown electric field strength in air of $\approx 30\text{kV}$, there is a minimum magnetic dipole

moment m for which the magnetic force will always exceed the electrostatic force, and the plasma will always be contained. The capacitance of a spherical semiconducting particle of radius a is $C = 4\pi\epsilon_0 a$, and since capacitance is defined as $C = q/V$, we have $q_{max} = 4\pi\epsilon_0 aV$. Substitution of this expression for q_{max} and $r_c = 2a$ into equation 7 above and rearranging yields the minimum value of the magnetic dipole moment per particle, m_{min} , required to confine the particles when charged to voltage V :

$$m_{min} = \frac{8\pi\epsilon_0 c}{\sqrt{6\kappa}} a^2 V = \frac{2.05 \times 10^5}{\sqrt{\kappa}} a^2 \text{ in units of Am}^2 \quad (8)$$

Recall that $\kappa = 1$ for perfect head-to-tail chaining of the magnetic particles. A value of 0.1 would be a reasonable value to assume for a partially ordered 3-D aggregate of particles. Values of m_{min} and the magnetization M_{min} (m_{min} times particle volume) are provided in Table 3 for a range of particle size.

Table 3. Magnetization requirements. Magnetic dipole moment per particle and magnetization required to maintain confinement of an orb for particles charged to the breakdown electric field strength of air of 30 kV and assuming $\kappa=0.1$, as calculated from equation 8.

Diameter, nm	m_{min} , Am ²	M_{min} , Am ⁻¹
10	1.6×10^{-14}	3.0×10^3
50	4.0×10^{-13}	6.0×10^2
100	1.6×10^{-12}	3.0×10^2
200	6.4×10^{-12}	1.5×10^2
500	4.0×10^{-11}	6.0×10^1
1,000 (1 μ m)	1.6×10^{-10}	3.0×10^1

The magnetic dipole moments required for electrostatic containment of a charged particulate plasma are modest and fall well within the range reported for meteoritic dust and interplanetary particles (29, 30). For particle radii between 5 and 500 nm, the minimum required magnetic moments range from 10^{-14} to 10^{-10} Am², corresponding to magnetizations of only 30-3,000 Am⁻¹. These values are orders of magnitude below the saturation magnetization of metallic iron, magnetite, or Fe–Ni alloys, and are consistent with partially oxidized or defect-rich meteoritic particles. Laboratory measurements of chondritic interplanetary dust particles (IDPs) and micrometeorites commonly report remanent magnetic moments equal to or exceeding these values, particularly for aggregates containing nanophase Fe or magnetite. Detailed magnetic studies of micrometeorites demonstrate that nanophase metallic iron, magnetite, and related Fe-bearing phases dominate their remanent magnetization, even in particles that are otherwise largely oxidized or amorphous (31, 32). Thus, self-confinement of a maximally charged meteoritic plasma does not require exotic materials or extreme magnetization and could arise naturally from the known magnetic properties of meteoritic dust even under maximal atmospheric charging conditions.

Energy Harvesting from the Atmosphere

In addition to plasma containment, the source of energy required for buoyancy, maintenance of the plasma and emission of light is enigmatic. Reports to NUFORC indicate that orbs may remain buoyant and continuously emit light over periods of three hours or longer. For emission of light alone, we estimate that the power consumption would be ~10 watts to produce a light intensity comparable to Venus for an orb at a distance of 1 km. Over three hours, this amounts to a minimum total energy requirement of 10.8 kJ. Considering that only a small fraction of expended energy would be light, orbs require an energy source on the order of 100 kJ or more. If some of the iron and/or nickel remains only partially oxidized, then continued air oxidation could provide that amount of energy. The complete oxidation of Fe to Fe₂O₃, for example, would produce 826 kJ/mol or 14.8 kJ per g of elemental Fe. Thus, of the order of 10 grams of elemental or partially oxidized iron could potentially provide enough energy to power the electrical discharge and associated light emission while also providing buoyancy with waste heat—but by what mechanism? Ambient oxidation (rusting) of iron is slow in the absence of a catalyst and doesn't by itself provide a mechanism for conversion of chemical to electrical energy to maintain a plasma with emission of light. Oxidation of elemental iron and magnetite also destroys remanence and thus confinement of the plasma.

Triboelectric charging. In the absence of a chemical energy source, we are left with the possibility that orbs harvest their energy from the atmosphere in some way. We hypothesize that this is accomplished via conversion of the mechanical energy of atmospheric shear and turbulence to electrical energy through the triboelectric effect (32, 33). Although still not fully understood due to its complexity, electrostatic effects due to rubbing two dissimilar materials together have been known at least since the fifth century BC (34). Tribocharging of particles in wood processing plants, grain elevators, coal mines, flour mills and many other industrial facilities results in ignition of many fires and explosions annually (35,36), while electric field strengths in dust storms can result in lightning on both Earth (37,38) and Mars (39). Tribocharging underlies lightning in thunderstorms and ash clouds of active volcanoes as well. Thus, tribocharging is common in the atmosphere.

Ablation and oxidation of stony meteoroids produce a heterogeneous mixture of particle types, dominated by silica and iron and nickel oxides, with smaller contributions from other mineral phases. Meteoric dust is primarily composed of nanoparticles with characteristic sizes of tens of nanometers (40, 41). This combination of particle size and chemical diversity is well suited for the generation of electrical currents through triboelectric charging during repeated particle contacts. Iron oxide nanoparticles have been widely investigated as active components in triboelectric nanogenerators, demonstrating their ability to participate efficiently in charge transfer when paired with dissimilar materials (42-46). While mixtures of iron and nickel oxides alone can support triboelectric charging, the presence of a chemically and electronically distinct phase such as silica is expected to enhance charge separation and increase the magnitude of triboelectrically driven currents. In mixed aggregates of this type, differences in conductivity, surface states, and magnetic properties may naturally lead to complementary roles among particle populations during

charging and discharge, while magnetic interactions among iron-bearing phases can provide a stabilizing skeletal framework for the aggregate.

Here it is hypothesized that an orb consists of a loosely bound ensemble of nanometer-to-micrometer sized particles, some of which are magnetic, in weakly ionized air. The particles are dynamically mixed by atmospheric shear, turbulence and internal convection, producing repeated contact–separation and near-contact events that result in charge transfer between particles. The net binding magnetic force likely contributes to the strength of the triboelectric effect by maintaining close contact between particles. Triboelectric charging produces a bipolar population of electron-rich and electron-poor particles, eliminating the need for a single macroscopic counter-electrode. Localized electric fields are amplified at particle asperities and transient gaps, producing distributed microdischarges at and near the orb surface that allow electrical currents to close locally through short, ionized paths in the surrounding sheath, as illustrated in Fig. 5. The orb may be modeled as an effective capacitor weakly and locally coupled to the surrounding air through resistive, nonlinear discharge pathways. Electrical energy is not stored for long periods but is continuously regenerated by mechanical agitation (churning) of the particles. Once initiated, a weakly ionized corona can facilitate continued electrical activity by increasing the local charge-carrier density and conductivity, supplying seed electrons and ions for subsequent avalanches, and reshaping the electric field through space-charge effects that localize breakdown to microdischarges with the surrounding sheath.

Fig. 5. Simplified model of triboelectric circuit. Triboelectric interactions among magnetically confined particles generate a bipolar population of electron-rich and electron-poor particles. Charge separation is spatially distributed, with multiple micro-cathodes and micro-anodes forming within the particle ensemble. Electrons emitted into the surrounding sheath participate in short-range ionization, drift, and recombination processes and are recollected locally, allowing electrical currents to close through networks of transient, ionized paths in the near field. Curved arrows indicate representative circulating charge motion within the orb–sheath system; dashed trajectories illustrate local discharge pathways rather than a net current to the distant environment.

Origins of colored emissions. Microdischarges excite molecular nitrogen in the surrounding air, generating the observed bluish-white emissions from the second positive system of nitrogen ($C^3\Pi_u \rightarrow B^3\Pi_g$) in the 350-450 nm wavelength range typical of discharges in air. Other colors of light may originate from excitation of metal atoms and their ions, especially Fe (yellow-orange), Ni (pale green, blue-white), Na (yellow), Ca (red, orange) and Mg (blue-white). Absorbance of emissions within the orb, especially by iron oxides, could contribute to the orange and red colors of many orbs. Incandescence of particles heated by discharges may also contribute to orange and red emissions as well. Optical spectra of orb emissions would be extremely helpful in understanding the origins of the wide range of observed orb color.

Consideration of chemiluminescence contributions to orb emissions. Persistent afterglows of varying color along meteor trajectories, known as “trains,” can last from minutes to hours and have been documented for more than a millennium (47). These phenomena, however, occur primarily in the mesosphere and thermosphere, where low ambient pressure and correspondingly low collisional quenching rates permit efficient chemiluminescent emissions. At such altitudes, reactions involving NO, O atoms, and O₃—analogous in some respects to auroral processes—can produce visible green, red, and near-infrared light. Although electrical discharges in air also generate NO, O, and O₃, these chemiluminescent pathways are unlikely to contribute significantly to orb emission in the lower atmosphere. At tropospheric pressures, rapid three-body recombination of O atoms to form O₃ and efficient collisional quenching of electronically excited NO₂ strongly suppress radiative emission due to pressure being orders of magnitude higher than in the mesosphere and thermosphere. As a result, such reactions cannot account for the observed brightness and persistence of orb emissions in the lower atmosphere. These considerations instead point to high-energy electronic excitation associated with localized plasma formation and distributed microdischarges as the dominant source of visible light emission in orbs.

Energy throughput. Nanoparticles are especially effective at tribocharging, motivating their widespread use in triboelectric generators (48). Although the absolute charge carried by an individual particle decreases with surface area, the number of particles produced from a given meteoroid mass scales as the inverse cube of particle diameter. Consequently, reducing particle size from the micrometer to nanometer scale increases the total rate of particle–particle contacts and near-contact interactions by up to three orders of magnitude, resulting in large increases in electrical current.

Order-of-magnitude estimates demonstrate that the required electrical throughput is modest on a per-particle basis. For a 1-m-diameter orb radiating approximately 10 W of visible light, the required electrical power is plausibly tens of watts. At effective discharge potentials of 1–10 kV, 100 W corresponds to currents of only 10–100 mA. For a representative case in which a 10-cm meteoroid is converted into 10–100 nm particles, and only ~1% of those particles actively participate in charge cycling at any given time, the required electron transfer rate is calculated to be of the order 0.1–10 electrons per second per active particle. Such rates are well within the range implied by known aerosol charging, flow electrification, and dust-storm electrification

phenomena, particularly in environments where weak ionization and microdischarges continually replenish charge carriers (49, 50).

Mechanical energy extracted from atmospheric shear and turbulence provides a natural power source. The kinetic energy flux available scales with air density, cross-sectional area, and the cube of the relative flow speed. For meter-scale orbs, relative air motions of a few meters per second—readily achieved in nocturnal boundary layers, inversion layers, and persistent shear or eddy structures—can supply tens of watts of mechanical power. In this proposed mechanism, energy is converted into electrical excitation through triboelectric and contact-charging processes and ultimately dissipated through microdischarges, with only a small fraction appearing as visible light.

Orb Strength and Lifespan

Although net attractive forces between individual particles are relatively weak, it is likely that aggregates of particles can be sufficiently strong to maintain integrity, at least in fair weather conditions. In addition to the dipole-dipole interactions of head-to-tail orientations of magnetized particles, there are analogous dipole-induced dipole interactions that attract unmagnetized ferromagnetic materials to a magnet. Thus, an orb is likely a disorganized aggregate of loosely bound particles whose rate of agglomeration is slowed by mutual electrostatic repulsion. Figure 6 shows an orb observed near ground level that was reported to approach a tree, apparently make contact with the upper branches (likely partially discharging to Earth ground), and then retreat and hover (51).

Fig. 6. Photo from NUFORC report 193124 showing the internal structure of a near-ground-level orb. The active discharge is best viewed in the video filed with this report.

A video recorded during the subsequent hovering stage shows ongoing discharges with multicolored emissions, while the internal plasma glow is greatly diminished. Under these conditions, a structured, globular mass becomes visible, proposed here to consist of an aggregate

of meteoric dust particles. Such behavior is consistent with a charge-depleted orb in which sustained triboelectric charging and microdischarge activity have weakened. As particles agglomerate, the effective particle size increases, reducing the efficiency of tribocharging and the ability to maintain localized discharges. The associated decline in electrical heating diminishes buoyancy, causing the orb to sink to lower altitudes. Ultimately, descent may culminate in discharge to a grounded object at the surface, followed by dissipation and deposition of particulate material. Orb lifetimes of minutes to hours would be dependent on factors like particle composition, size distribution, degree of magnetization and meteorological conditions.

Discussion

The triboelectric–discharge model plausibly explains many reported features of luminous orbs: long lifetimes (minutes to hours), weak mutual bonding, splitting and merging behavior, flickering and blinking emission, induction of light emission in nearby non-emitting orbs, and pronounced color variability. Importantly, the model does not require large reservoirs of stored electrostatic energy or strong global ionization; instead, luminosity is sustained through continuous, distributed energy conversion driven by ambient atmospheric motions. As such, it provides a physically grounded mechanism by which a weakly ionized dusty plasma can remain luminous and dynamically active for extended periods of time.

Because electrical breakdown is threshold-dependent, modest fluctuations in pressure, humidity, particle concentration, or local electric field strength naturally lead to intermittent discharge behavior, producing the observed blinking and flickering of orbs. Weakly charged orbs must accumulate additional charge before re-initiating discharge, while more strongly charged orbs can perturb the local electric field sufficiently to induce emission in nearby non-emitting or weakly emitting orbs, consistent with reports of “dark” orbs becoming luminous in the presence of active ones.

A magnetically confined dusty plasma also provides a natural explanation for orb division and merging. Weak inter-orb binding mediated by charge-induced dipole and higher-order multipole interactions would be expected, analogous to van der Waals forces between molecules, and could result in merging. From an energetic perspective, there may exist preferred orb sizes for given combinations of mass, particle size, charge state, and magnetic strength, such that mechanical stresses from wind shear or turbulence favor splitting into multiple smaller aggregates.

Orb division resulting in orbs of different colors may result from partial phase separation during splitting, yielding separate orb fragments with differing particle compositions or size distributions (e.g., silica-rich versus iron-rich fractions). Also, mutual electrostatic repulsion drives smaller particles toward the aggregate periphery, while larger particles remain preferentially concentrated toward the interior, making asymmetric partitioning during division likely. Because smaller particles are more efficient triboelectric generators, these asymmetries could naturally produce differences in discharge energy and emission wavelengths among the resulting orbs.

As an illustrative example of orb fluidity and cohesion, publicly released video footage from a September 9, 2025 U.S. House of Representatives hearing on unidentified aerial phenomena shows an orb impacted by a projectile (Hellfire Missile), followed by fragmentation

into smaller globules (52). While interpretation of such imagery is necessarily limited, this behavior would be expected if a magnetically confined dusty plasma were impacted by a blunt object—the fragments would be expected to clump back together after separating.

Here, we argue that luminous orbs represent a rare but physically real atmospheric phenomenon. Any model capable of addressing their origin, containment, fluidity, plasma-like behavior, energy source, and light emission is necessarily unconventional. However, the strong correlation between orb observations and meteor activity reported here provides a solid physical starting point. Although novel in several respects, the proposed framework is based on established physical principles, and its components are testable through laboratory experiments, targeted atmospheric measurements, and more detailed theoretical modeling. It may even be possible to generate orbs in the laboratory from magnetic nanoparticles.

In addition to scientific interest, orbs have acquired substantial popular cultural significance. Providing a physics-based explanation has the potential to resolve a large fraction of reported UAP sightings and reduce public anxiety associated with these rare and poorly understood events. Orbs are routinely reported by civilian and military pilots and may constitute an air traffic hazard. Orbs could be an unrecognized ignition source for wildfires, especially in grasslands. On the positive side, there could be applications of synthetic orbs such as long-lasting flares for search and rescue operations or new types of triboelectric generators. Since orbs occur on Earth, similar phenomena almost certainly occur on other planets having atmospheres, making further study of this interesting phenomenon highly relevant to planetary and space science as well.

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4. UFOs (Unidentified Flying Objects) were rebranded as UAPs (Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena) by the U.S. government beginning with the Navy-led UAP Task Force in 2020. The purpose of the shift was to include transmedium (air/sea) objects rather than only flying ones and to move away from pop-culture connotations of alien spacecraft and focus on serious scientific investigation.
5. NUFORC UFO Sighting reports for orb images in Figure 1 are: a (192492), b (185621), c (185625), d (182271), e (168160), f (183903) and g (179226). Links to the reports are <https://nuforc.org/sighting?id=xxxxxx/> where xxxxxx is the sighting number.
6. A corona and multicolored microdischarges are visible in the video of NUFORC UFO Sighting 185621: <https://nuforc.org/sighting/?id=185621>.
7. Long distance bonding is evident in the video of three blue and green orbs in final photo of this report: NUFORC UFO Sighting 168160, <https://nuforc.org/sighting/?id=168160>.
8. In one example of splitting, a yellow-orange orb begins to flash at time ~3:30, then suddenly splits into two orbs at ~3:38 that then move together. The report includes observations of splitting into three orbs that form a triangle and merging of orbs as well. Note that the orb exists in presence of distant lightning activity. NUFORC UFO Sighting 183546, <https://nuforc.org/sighting/?id=183546>.
9. This report contains the video of Fig. 2 and is the best example found of orbs merging and splitting. Also evident in the video are orbs being captured in one another's electric fields, formation of a triangle of orbs, and what appears to be enhanced emissions following splitting and induced emission in an orb that had become dark. NUFORC Video 194306, <https://nuforc.org/sighting/?id=194306>.
10. Bright white orbs appear to pop into and out of existence in the video of NUFORC UFO Sighting 178910 as the plasma ignites and extinguishes: <https://nuforc.org/sighting/?id=178910>.
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